

(Re)solving reionisation with high-redshift analogues at cosmic noon

Jorjy Matthee

Department of Physics, ETH Zürich, Wolfgang-Pauli-Strasse 27, 8093 Zürich, Switzerland

Thanks to its intrinsic brightness and rest-frame UV wavelength, the Ly α line (Ly α , $\lambda_0 = 1215.67 \text{ \AA}$) is a key observable in studies of galaxies in the early Universe. Thousands of so-called Ly α emitters (LAEs) have been identified over $z \approx 2 - 7$ thanks to their strong Ly α emission, typically with wide-field narrow-band surveys or in IFU data-sets (e.g., [1, 2]). However, the role of the LAE population, for example their contribution to the cosmic star formation density or the cosmic ionising emissivity) is relatively unknown due to uncertainties and complexities in the Ly α radiative transfer that impact the fraction of produced Ly α photons that reach our telescopes.

Due to the high cross section, Ly α photons resonantly scatter in the presence of neutral hydrogen. This increases the travelled path length and therefore the possibility of dust absorption. The precise magnitude of this effect depends on the velocity field and column density distribution and clumpiness of neutral gas and dust in a complex way. This leads to the uncertainties in the escape fraction. However, another consequence is that the detailed properties of the Ly α line such as its line-profile offer the opportunity to trace the HI in and around galaxies. In particular, the Ly α line-profile can be used to constrain properties as the escape fraction of ionising photons (e.g., [3, 4]).

Empirically, however, the Ly α production rate, the escape fraction and the line-profile are poorly understood at high-redshift. This is due to the typical limited spectral resolution and the lack of rest-frame optical spectra required to measure the intrinsic luminosity and systemic redshift. Addressing these issues is the key motivation for undertaking the X-SHOOTER Lyman- α survey at $z = 2$ (XLS- $z2$; [5]).

The X-SHOOTER Lyman- α survey at $z = 2$

Currently, cosmic noon ($z \sim 2$) is the ideal redshift to study LAEs in detail. This is because i) a clean selection-function of LAEs is challenging to obtain at lower redshift as space-based UV spectroscopy is required, ii) redshift $z \approx 2$ is the highest redshift where H α is observable from the ground, as it shifts out of the K_s band at $z > 2.5$. Without H α , it is practically challenging to infer the nebular dust attenuation and therefore the intrinsic line-luminosity and iii) the age of the Universe is relatively short at $z \approx 2$, which makes the range of allowed star formation histories (SFHs) of LAEs comparable to the SFHs of very high-redshift galaxies.

We have undertaken the XLS- $z2$ survey using deep VLT/X-SHOOTER observations of 35 LAEs at $z \sim 2$. The typical exposure times are 3.5 hours and the X-SHOOTER data cover rest-frame wavelengths from $\lambda_0 \approx 1000 - 7000 \text{ \AA}$ with a resolution $R \approx 4000 - 7000$.

The LAEs have primarily been selected using wide-field narrow-band surveys in well-known extra-galactic fields as COSMOS and UDS (see [5] for details). They are representative of the relatively bright ($> 0.2 L^*$) LAEs that are commonly found in deep narrow-band surveys (e.g., [2]) or IFU observations (e.g., [1]). The typical stellar mass of the LAEs is $10^9 M_\odot$, which is lower than the mass of continuum-selected star-forming galaxies that are commonly studied at $z \approx 2$. Systemic red-shifts are measured from rest-frame optical lines for 33/35 sources. The Ly α lines are observed with high S/N, see Figure 1 for a few examples. We find that the majority of Ly α lines ($\approx 75 \%$) show a double-peaked profile with a dominant red peak.

Figure 1: A few example Ly α profiles of XLS- $z2$ LAEs with a resolution of $R \approx 4000$ (adapted from [5]). Blue lines show the data and the grey shaded region illustrates the 1σ noise level. The velocity range of the spectra are centred on their measured systemic red-shifts. Ly α lines are characterised by a red-dominant double-peaked profile.

What makes galaxies LAEs?

The first fundamental question that we addressed with XLS- $z2$ is “What makes galaxies’ LAEs?”. This is of importance in order to extrapolate results on LAEs to the general galaxy population. Owing to the faintness of the individual LAEs, we used stacking techniques to obtain a detailed view of the average LAE [5]. The wide-band coverage of X-SHOOTER allowed measurements of faint absorption features from interstellar absorption lines (e.g., SiII), UV emission lines (e.g., HeII, CIV, OIII]), rest-frame optical lines ([OIII], [NeIII], H β , [OIII], H α) that we used to infer the typical properties of LAEs at $z \approx 2$. We further used high-resolution rest-frame UV imaging data from *HST*/ACS. We find that:

- LAEs are characterized by an interstellar medium with little dust, a low $\approx 1/10 Z_{\odot}$ gas-phase metallicity, and a high ionization state.
- The ionizing sources in LAEs are young (≈ 10 Myr) hot stars that power the high equivalent widths of emission lines in the optical and high-ionization lines in the ultraviolet.
- The rest-frame UV morphology is clumpy. LAEs show outflowing kinematics with blue-shifted SII absorption, a broad [O III] component, and a red-skewed Ly α line.
- Typically, 30 per cent of the Ly α photons escape, and a quarter of these photons escape on the blue side of the systemic velocity.

Figure 2: Illustration of the relevant properties that determine whether galaxies are observed as LAEs (left) or not (right). LAEs have young stars (blue), a low dust content (red dots), a low HI column density (grey shade), and, possibly, HI-free channels (white channels). These conditions are more often present in low-mass galaxies than in high-mass galaxies at $z \approx 2$.

Figure 2 summarises a physical picture of the properties that we identify to determine whether galaxies are observed as LAEs. A low dust content and an ongoing starburst are prerequisite in order to be a LAE. These conditions are common in relatively low-mass galaxies and this therefore explains – to first order – why LAEs have lower masses than typical continuum-selected galaxies. However, at fixed mass, LAEs are not particularly dust-free, nor are the stars particularly young. Therefore, we conclude that especially the *effective* HI column density determines the apparent Ly α luminosity of a galaxy. This could be either related to outflows that disperse the gas and create HI-free channels, or due to a fortunate viewing angle. Future comparable observations of carefully-matched samples (i.e. in mass, attenuation and star formation activity) of non-LAEs can distinguish which of these effects is most important.

Ongoing work to (re)solve reionisation

In [5], we argue, based on luminosity functions and Ly α statistics, that the conditions that facilitate Ly α escape are relatively rare at $z \approx 2$, but appear more common

in the very early Universe (i.e. $z > 6$). It is therefore of interest to measure the contribution of LAEs to the ionising emissivity, which particularly requires us to know their escape fraction of ionising photons (LyC photons). In ongoing work, we are analysing the variety in the Ly α line-profiles (e.g., Figure 1) as a way of indirectly inferring the LyC escape fraction [3]. While this is admittedly indirect, we note that such measurement of the escape fraction is not subject to the stochasticity in sightlines through the intergalactic medium that plagues direct LyC measurements in individual galaxies at high-redshift.

Our tentative results are very promising: we find that half the LAEs at $z \approx 2$ have line-profiles suggestive of a high ($> 20\%$) escape fraction of ionising photons, while few ionising photons escape from other LAEs. The LyC-leaking subset of LAEs *simultaneously* shows remarkably different properties in the ISM and stellar populations, with a lower dust attenuation, weaker interstellar absorption, gas that is optically thin to MgII photons and younger and (much) hotter stellar populations [6]. This demonstrates that the phase during which galaxies have an ISM structure that allows the leakage of ionising photons coincides with the time when the hottest stars shine their ionising photons.

Thanks to the well-defined selection function of XLS- $z2$ we can place these results into a cosmological context. If we assume the ionising properties (i.e. production and escape) of LAEs to be redshift-invariant, bright LAEs form the sub-population of the star-forming galaxy population that dominates the ionising emissivity at early times and, together with quasars, explains the evolution of the ionising background over $z \approx 2 - 8$. A small fraction of the total galaxy population is thus an effective ioniser, and the LAE statistics allow us to explain how this fraction increases strongly with redshift (with the population-averaged escape fraction increasing by $\propto (1+z)^3$ from $z \approx 2 - 8$). Simultaneously, a Ly α -luminosity linked ionising contribution yields an optimal stellar mass of $\approx 10^8 M_{\odot}$ of the galaxies that are contributing most to the emissivity [7]. In the future, we aim to test this LAE-framework by extending observations to fainter luminosities and higher red-shifts. This will particularly benefit from joint spectroscopic observations of VLT/MUSE and the *James Webb Space Telescope* tracing the rest-frame ultraviolet and optical of galaxies at $z > 3$, respectively.

References

- [1] Herenz, C., et al. 2019, A&A, 621, 107
- [2] Sobral, D., et al. 2018, MNRAS, 476, 4725
- [3] Izotov, Y., et al. 2018, MNRAS, 478, 4851
- [4] Verhamme, A., et al. 2015, A&A, 578, 7
- [5] Matthee, J., et al. 2021, MNRAS, 505, 1382
- [6] Naidu, R.P. et al., in prep.
- [7] Matthee, J., et al., in prep.

Short CV

2014: Master in Astronomy, Leiden University, The Netherlands
 2018: PhD in Astronomy, Leiden University, The Netherlands
 2018-present: Zwicky Fellow, ETH Zurich, Switzerland